

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

COLLEGE OF ALLIED HEALTH SCIENCES

PROCEEDINGS OF THE MEETING OF BOARD OF STUDIES HELD ON 05.03.2019 AT 9:30 AM IN THE BOARD ROOM

Members present:

1. Dr. Sham Kishore	Chairman
2. Mr. Naveen Bappanadu	Member
3. Dr. Sukesh	Member
4. Dr. Pavanchand Attavar	Member
5. Dr. Vishrutha K V	Member
6. Ms. Shristina Subba	Member
7. Ms. Sathyajith Karanth	Member
8. Dr. Sangeetha	Member
9. Ms. Laveena D'Souza	Member
10. Ms. Swathi D	Member
11. Mrs. Shwetha B	External Member
12. Dr. Vrinda	External Member

Leave of Absence:

Leave of Absence was granted to the following members by the Chairman of Board of Studies:

1. Mr. Naveen Bappanadu (Member)
2. Mrs. Shwetha B (Member)

The BOS discussed the following agenda:

1. Approve the minutes of the last Meeting of the BOS held on 08.10.2018.
2. Approve the Finalized updates and changes Proposed for Academic Session 2018-19.
3. Approval of new program in Allied Health Science.
4. Finalize the Internship requirement of the courses of Allied Health Sciences.
5. Discussion regarding Value-Added courses.
6. Commencement of few M.Sc. Courses in Allied Health Sciences.
7. Revise Few Topics in the Course of 'Renal Dialysis Technology'.

The Chairman Dr. Sham Kishore introduced himself, thanking and welcoming all the members who were present for the meeting. The meeting there after deliberated on agenda as had been approved by the Chairperson.

Agenda No. 1: Confirmations of the minutes of Last Meeting of Board of Studies which was held on 17.10.2018. As per the suggestions of the BOS Members in the last meeting, all the Allied Health Sciences Courses were asked to update the changes proposed by the BOS Members.

Agenda No. 2: The Finalized Updates and changes were proposed by the BOS for the Academic Session 2019-20 (Reference Page 3, Table 1) and had to be approved. Resolution was taken accordingly; updates and changes were approved as proposed by the BOS.

Agenda No. 3: As per the suggestion of the BOS members the new program B.Sc. Cardiac Care Technology was added in Allied Health Science from the Academic Year 2019-20 and the same was approved by the Chairman.

Agenda No. 4: All the courses of Allied Health Sciences, as already decided for 6 months internship after the 6th semester along with the clinical posting to Srinivas hospital on roaster duty to gain hands on experience. It was approved by BOS as recommended.

Agenda No. 5: As per the suggestion of the BOS regarding the Value-Added Courses, Department of Renal Dialysis Technology suggested a course, “Life of Peritoneal Dialysis”, Department of Perfusion Technology suggested, “Advance in Cannulation technique and Department of Medical Laboratory Technology suggested two Value-Added courses such as Quality Control management and Laboratory Safety management. The resolution was taken accordingly for the Academic Year 2019 regarding the Value-Added courses and the same was approved by the BOS.

Agenda No. 6: Discussion regarding the addition of the M.Sc. Courses in Allied Health Sciences, in the Academic Year 2020-21. The BOS approved that the M.Sc. Courses were to be added in the Academic Year 2020-21.

Agenda No. 7: To Revise the Topics of the course of ‘Renal dialysis Technology’ was suggested by Dr. Ravi Bhaskar and Sr. Faculty Ms. Shristina Subba. The Revised Topics were confirmed and was approved by the BOS as suggested.

The meeting was concluded at 11:30 AM with a vote of thanks by Ms. Swathi D, Member and Board of Studies.

Dr. Sham Kishore,
Chairman,
BOS in Allied Health Science

Table 1

Addition and Deletion in main subjects, subsidiary, topics in All Allied Health Courses

Course	Topics added/ deleted on BOS proposal	Reason
RDT	Addition: 6 th semester: Renal Diet & Nutrition (Newly added) Renal Transplantation. (Newly added) Peritoneal dialysis. (Newly added) Hospital Management. (Newly added) Electrocardiography (Newly added) Basic Radiography. (Newly added)	The topics which are required in the field and is latest

Table 2

Courses approved for the academic year 2019-2020

Sl. No	Name of the Coursework
1.	B.Sc. Cardiac Care Technology
2.	M.Sc. MLT in Clinical Biochemistry
3.	M.Sc. MLT in Hematology and Blood transfusion
4.	M.Sc. MLT in Microbiology and Immunology
5.	M.Sc. Echocardiography
6.	M.Sc. Cardiac Catheterization and Intervention
7.	M.Sc. Respiratory Care Technology
8.	M.Sc. Medical Imaging Technology
9.	M.Sc. Anesthesia and Operation Theatre Technology

Members present:

Dr. Sham Kishore

Dr. Sukesh

Dr. Pavanchand Attavar

Dr. Vishrutha K V

Ms. Haritha Chandran

Ms. Shristina Subba

Dr. Sathyajith Karanth

Dr. Sangeetha

Ms. Laveena D'Souza

Ms. Swathi D